

P-ADIC DYNAMICAL SYSTEMS OF THE FUNCTION AX^{-K}

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Abstract. In this talk we consider the dynamical systems generated by the function $f(x) = \frac{a}{x^k}$ in the field of p -adic numbers \mathbb{Q}_p .

To define a dynamical system we consider a function $f : x \in U \rightarrow f(x) \in U$. For $x \in U$ denote by $f^n(x)$ the n -fold composition of f with itself (i.e. n time iteration of f to x):

$$f^n(x) = \underbrace{f(f(f(\dots(f(x))))\dots)}$$

For arbitrary given $x_0 \in U$ and $f : U \rightarrow U$ the discrete-time dynamical system (also called the trajectory) of x_0 is the sequence of points:

$$x_0, x_1 = f(x_0), x_2 = f(x_1) = f^2(x_0), x_3 = f(x_2) = f^3(x_0), \dots, x_n = f^n(x_0), \dots$$

This expression is called the *orbit* of the point x_0 under the influence of the function $f(x)$. Where point x_0 is called the *origin of the orbit*.

A point $x \in U$ is called a fixed point for f if $f(x) = x$. The point x is a periodic point of period m if $f^m(x) = x$. The least positive m for which $f^m(x) = x$ is called the prime period of x . A fixed point x_0 is called an *attractor* if there exist a neighborhood $U(x_0)$ of x_0 such that for all points $x \in U(x_0)$ it holds $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f^n(x) = x_0$. If x_0 is an attractor then its *basin of attraction* is

$$A(x_0) = \{x \in \mathbb{R} : f^n(x) \rightarrow x_0, n \rightarrow \infty\}.$$

A fixed point x_0 is called *repeller* if there exists a neighborhood $U(x_0)$ of x_0 such that $|f(x) - x_0|_p > |x - x_0|_p$ for $x \in U(x_0)$, $x \neq x_0$. Let x_0 be a fixed point of a function $f(x)$. Put $\lambda = f'(x_0)$. The point x_0 is *attractive* if $0 < |\lambda|_p < 1$, *indifferent* if $|\lambda|_p = 1$, and *repelling* if $|\lambda|_p > 1$.

The ball $U_r(x_0)$ (contained in V) is said to be a *Siegel disk* if each sphere $S_\rho(x_0)$, $\rho < r$ is an invariant sphere of $f(x)$, i.e. if $x \in S_\rho(x_0)$, then all iterated points $f^n(x) \in S_\rho(x_0)$ for all $n=1,2,\dots$. The union of all Siegel disks with the center at x_0 is called a *maximum Siegel disk* and is denoted by $SI(x_0)$.

In this work we consider the discrete dynamical system associated with the function $f : \mathbb{Q}_p \rightarrow \mathbb{Q}_p$ defined by

$$f(x) = \frac{a}{x^k}, \quad a \neq 0, \quad a \in \mathbb{Q}_p, \quad k \in \mathbb{N}, \quad \text{where } x \neq \hat{x} = 0. \quad (1)$$

The fixed points of this function are solutions of the equation $x^{k+1} = a$ in \mathbb{Q}_p . The work provides detailed information about the solutions of the equation $x^k = a$ in the field \mathbb{Q}_p . Using these data, we obtain the following results. Define the set

$$Sol_p(x^{k+1} - a) = \{\xi \in \mathbb{F}_p : \xi^{k+1} \equiv a \pmod{p}\}, \quad a \in \mathbb{Z}_p^*,$$

where $\mathbb{F}_p := \{0, 1, 2, \dots, p-1\}$ and $\mathbb{Z}_p^* := \{x \in \mathbb{Q} : |x|_p = 1\}$. We also denote the number of elements of the set $Sol_p(x^{k+1} - a)$ by k_p . Note that for any number $k \in \mathbb{N}$, there are numbers $m \in \mathbb{N}$ and $s \in \mathbb{Z}_+$ such that $k = mp^s$, $(m, p) = 1$ is valid. Let

$$a = a_0 + a_1 \cdot p + a_2 \cdot p^2 + a_3 \cdot p^3 + \dots \quad (2).$$

Theorem 1. Let $p \geq 3$ and $k + 1 = mp^s$. If the canonical expansion of the number $a \in \mathbb{Z}_p^*$ is (2), then the following assertions are valid:

- (i) If $Sol_p(x^{k+1} - a) = \emptyset$ then the equation $x^{k+1} = a$ hasn't solution;
- (ii) Let $Sol_p(x^{k+1} - a) \neq \emptyset$. Then
 - (ii)1) if $|a - a_0^{p^s}|_p \geq p^{-s}$, then the equation $x^{k+1} = a$ hasn't solution;
 - (ii)2) if $|a - a_0^{p^s}|_p < p^{-s}$, then the number of solutions of the equation $x^{k+1} = a$

is equal to κ_p .

Theorem 2. Let $p \geq 3$ and let $a \in \xi_p$. Then the following assertions hold:

- (i) if $|k|_p \leq |a - 1|_p$, then (1) has no solution;
- (ii) if $|k|_p > |a - 1|_p$, then (1) has exactly κ_p solutions $x_{\xi_i} \in B_1(\xi_i), i \in \{1, 2, \dots, \kappa_p\}$,

where $\xi_i \in Sol_p(x^{k+1} - a)$.

It can be seen from this theorem that the number of fixed points of the function (1) may be equal to κ_p .

Theorem 3. Let $p \geq 3, k + 1 = mp^s, a \in \mathbb{Z}_p^*$ and $|a - a_0^{p^s}|_p < p^{-s}$. Then the fixed points of the function (1) is an attractive for $p|k$ and an indifferent for $p \nmid k$.

References

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